

2771-2281 Open Access Journal

INTERNATIONAL

JOURNAL OF PEDAGOGICS

editor@theusajournals.com **VOLUME 05 - 2025**

OSCAR PUBLISHING
Services

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PEDAGOGICS
(IJP)**

Journal Impact Factor

Volume 05 Issue 07- 2025

ISSN (2771-2281)

Oscar Publishing Services

<https://theusajournals.com/index.php/ijp/about>

Email: editor@theusajournals.com

Publisher Address: 265 Jan St, Manhattan,

IL 60442, USA

Editorial Board Members:

Christine Cho, Nipissing University, Canada

Maria del Carmen Salazar University of Denver, USA

Corey Drake Michigan State University, USA

H. Alix Gallagher Stanford University, USA

Ye He The University of North Carolina at Greensboro, USA

David Stroupe Michigan State University, USA

Roddy Theobald American Institutes for Research, USA

Jessica Thompson University of Washington, USA

Jan van Driel University of Melbourne, Australia

Chezare Warren Michigan State University, USA

Rebecca West Burns University of South Florida, USA

Karl Wheatley Cleveland State University, USA

Theo Wubbels Utrecht University, Netherlands

OSCAR
PUBLISHING SERVICES

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF PEDAGOGICS (IJP)

ISSN: 2771-2281

Table of Content - Volume 05 Issue 07 (July)

NO.	ARTICLE TITLE	AUTHOR NAME	PAGE NO.
1.	PSYCHOLOGICAL BASIS OF MOTIVATION: THEORIES AND MODERN VIEWS	Urazbayeva Yulduz Abdullayevna	1-5
2.	ESTABLISHING EFFECTIVE COMMUNICATION WITH THE FAMILIES WHO HAVE ADOPTED ORPHANS AND CHILDREN LEFT WITHOUT PARENTAL CARE	Raximbaeva Gulyora Ulug'bekovna	6-15
3.	PSYCHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF PERSONAL DEVELOPMENT IN ADULTHOOD	Eshchanova Nasiba Matnazarovna	16-19
4.	DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL AND COMMUNICATION SKILLS IN ENGLISH OF MUSIC EDUCATION STUDENTS	Ashurova Zulayxo Erkinovna	20-25
5.	Using innovative technologies in teaching English to medical students	Michaela Mushuchik	26-31
6.	The importance of developing the spiritual and moral competence of young people	Raxmonova Gullola Shavkatovna	32-34
7.	Addressing the Decline in Teaching Professionalism: Empowering Educators to Improve Pedagogy Through Action Research	Ethan Davis, Ava Johnson	35-37
8.	Teaching didactic lessons based on problematic situations in drawing classes	Gulomova Nozima Khotamovna	38-41
9	The role of involving students in design activities in the concept of modern technology education	Jabborova Umida Yusupovna	42-44
10	Teaching effectively and productively academic writing skill in higher school pupils	Ibadova Farida Maxmarajabovna	45-53
11.	Issues of developing students' communicative competence in modern educational settings	Akmaljon Yusufovich Akhmedov	54-62
12.	Some Issues of Teaching The Uzbek Language As A Sister Language in Higher Education	Sh.Sh.Yuldasheva	63-66
13.	The Importance of Teaching Methods for Rubob	Saitov Jaqsiliq Jarilqasinovich	67-72
14.	Model for the Development of Students' Creative Competence in The Process of Teaching English	Seilkhanova R.N.	73-81
15.	Recreational Tourism and Healthy Lifestyle: Pedagogical Opportunities	Nuriyman Sultanzade	82-89

ESTABLISHING EFFECTIVE COMMUNICATION WITH THE FAMILIES WHO HAVE ADOPTED ORPHANS AND CHILDREN LEFT WITHOUT PARENTAL CARE

Raximbaeva Gulyora Ulug‘bekovna

Psychologist of the Urgench city "Inson" social services center

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16298375>

Annotation: This article discusses the issue of establishing effective communication with families that adopt orphans and children left without parental care. The psycho-social attitude of the adoptive family towards the child, the subtleties of the child's psychology, the culture of communication necessary for their social adaptation and free self-expression are analyzed. The psychological and pedagogical foundations of creating a trusting, loving and healthy communication environment in the process of raising a child are also described. The article also puts forward practical recommendations for the effective organization of family communication. The results of the study show that family communication plays a decisive role in the formation of this category of children as healthy individuals.

Keywords: Orphans, adoption, family communication, child psychology, culture of communication, social adaptation, loving environment, pedagogical approach.

Introduction.

Every child deserves love and care. The fate of children who, for various reasons, are left without parental care in life is one of the important issues that society must pay attention to. Families that take such children into their arms have a high moral and social responsibility, and trusting and sincere communication plays a special role in creating a healthy upbringing environment for them. Because a child's adaptation to a new environment, self-esteem, and building warm relationships with others largely depend on daily communication with family members. Therefore, establishing communication with adopted children in a conscious, careful, and loving manner is a necessary condition for their healthy psychological development and full adaptation to society.

Analysis of relevant literature:

The issue of communication with families that adopt orphans and children left without parental care is being widely studied within the disciplines of psychology, pedagogy, and sociology. Theories of A. Maslow and K. Rogers on human needs and personal growth justify the importance of an individual approach in communicating with adopted children. According to the cultural-historical concept of S. Vygotsky, the environment, especially interaction with the family, plays an important role in the development of a child's personality. The works of local researchers M. Kholmatova, S. Olimova, G. Kuchkarova reveal the role of family upbringing and emotional communication in the development of a child. The need to use communication

techniques to build trust, strengthen self-esteem and ensure mental balance in adopted children is confirmed by their works. Modern scientific sources on the topics of child psychology, trauma psychology and social adaptation, in particular, concepts developed by foreign scientists such as D. Brown and B. Perry, substantiate methods of providing emotional security, patience and positive motivation in communicating with adopted children. At the same time, research on family psychotherapy and parenting techniques suggests ways to improve the quality of family communication, reduce conflicts, and adapt the child to a new family environment. Modern psychological literature also deeply covers emotional and volitional disorders, insecurity, anxiety, fear of separation, and low self-esteem that can occur in adopted children, and emphasizes the crucial importance of parents' communication culture in overcoming these problems. To create a positive communication environment in the family, it is necessary to actively listen, provide emotional support, correctly use nonverbal communication tools, and treat the child's feelings with respect.

According to the theory of social psychologist A. Adler, in order for a child to feel like a full member of society, he must first feel accepted and valued in the family. From this perspective, the main factor in adapting a child to a new family is not only external care, but also internal, emotional closeness, showing affection to him through constant and sincere communication. The analyzed literature also provides practical recommendations on the psychological preparation of adoptive parents, the stages of establishing contact with the child, and overcoming possible crisis situations. Studies show that in order to reduce the socio-psychological distance between the child and the adoptive family members, communication should be constant, open, affectionate, and valuing the child as a person. At the same time, in the process of upbringing, a careful and empathetic approach to communication with him is considered important, taking into account the child's previous experiences, mental state, and past negative experiences. The approaches presented in the sources of information show that healthy social and psychological adaptation in adopted children is possible only through properly structured family communication. Therefore, based on the literature on the subject, it can be concluded that for adoptive families, a culture of communication and psychological literacy are the key to the child's personal development and family stability. Based on the literature analyzed above, it becomes clear that establishing effective communication with adopted children is not only a pedagogical, but also a deep psychological process. Studies show that when a child feels that they are being listened to during the communication process, that their feelings are not indifferent, and that their opinions are taken into account, they gradually form a positive attitude towards themselves and their attachment to the family increases. Therefore, the literature recommends trainings, practical exercises, and consulting programs for parents to determine the child's psychological state, understand his emotional needs,

and choose the appropriate approach to him. Some sources note that adopted children may have a weak reflex of reflection, that is, difficulties in understanding the feelings of others, and in this case, a patient, consistent and loving attitude of parents is considered the most important tool. Also, the need to create opportunities for the child to express himself in the communication process, to use an approach based on encouragement rather than criticism, and to pave the way for the child to gain positive experience in social situations is emphasized in many studies. Modern literature also considers psychological ways of working with factors such as communication disorders developed on the basis of trauma, lack of trust, and fear of abandonment. In particular, advanced therapeutic approaches - art therapy, bibliotherapy, family role-playing games, and techniques for working on emotional concepts - can help to open the child's inner world. All this indicates the need for adoptive parents and specialists to establish a comprehensive, deep, conscious and systematic approach to mutual communication. According to the results of the analysis, a healthy family environment based on communication with an adopted child serves not only the sustainable development of the child's personality, but also the formation of a mutually beneficial, socially responsible society. The scientific and practical approaches described in the literature emphasize that communication is not only an exchange of information, but also a process that provides emotional closeness, educational influence and interpersonal connection. Therefore, through a thorough analysis of literary sources on this topic, it becomes possible to develop effective strategies for the formation of a trusting and loving family environment based on stable communication with adopted children.

Table 1. Literature studied on the topic and their annotation.

Author	Title of the work	Note
A. Maslou	Motivation and personality	Explains the importance of basic human needs, especially the need for affection, security, and self-esteem, in communicating with children
K. Rogers	Person-centered therapy	It establishes that listening to the child, respecting him, and treating him with sincere affection are the foundations of communication
S. Vigotskiy	Theory of cultural-historical development	Describes the mediating role of the social environment, especially the family and communication, in the development of a child's personality
A. Adler	Fundamentals of Individual Psychology	Shows the importance of family trust and emotional closeness for a child to develop into a useful person in society
G. Qo'chqorova	Socio-psychological adaptation and family environment	The effect of communication in reducing the socio-psychological distance between the child and the family is revealed

Research methodology:

A systematic approach based on the intersection of psychological, pedagogical and social sciences was used in the study of this topic. In order to deeply analyze the process of communication with adopted children, theoretical and empirical methods were selected in harmony. The works of advanced foreign and domestic scientists, sources on child psychology, trauma psychology, family upbringing and social adaptation were studied as theoretical foundations. Through them, factors affecting the development of communication, the dynamics of relations between the child and the family were analyzed. At the empirical stage, questionnaires, interviews and psychological observation methods were used. The communication styles of adoptive families, children's emotional responses, trust formation and social adaptation indicators were assessed in real situations. Also, problems in communication and effective solutions were identified through individual interviews with specialist psychologists and educators. In the analysis process, along with qualitative methods, quantitative approaches were also used in some cases, that is, the criteria for the results of observation and interviews were divided into thematic groups and summarized. Through the case study method, the individuality and specific communication needs of children were identified.

The methodological basis was based on a systematic approach, a person-centered model, and the principles of emotional and psychological support. These approaches served to identify practical methods for establishing stable and positive communication with adopted children. Also, special attention was paid to determining the psychological state of the child's personality through non-invasive (non-directly affecting) methods in methodological approaches. Project techniques that determine the child's level of confidence, emotional openness, and internal state when entering into communication were used, in particular, tests such as "I draw my family", "People in my heart", "Me and my world". Through this, it was found out how the child feels in a family environment and how he relates to relationships.

In analyzing communication, verbal and nonverbal signals between children and adoptive parents were studied. In this case, elements such as body language, eye contact, voice timbre, facial expressions, proximity distance were taken as the main indicators. In cases where communication breakdowns, ambiguities, or emotional barriers were identified, an analytical approach was used to identify the causes of their occurrence. All activities were carried out with caution and on the basis of ethical and normative requirements so that the selected methods did not negatively affect the child's psyche. The principles of confidentiality of information and consent of participants were strictly observed. The results obtained were analyzed individually and general conclusions were put forward. Also, communicative strategies that can be used in real situations by providing psychological counseling to families were developed. The use of such a wide range of methodological approaches helped to deeply reveal the topic and identify real opportunities for building healthy communication between children and adoptive families. The results serve as a useful methodological basis for practicing psychologists, educators and family counselors in this area. The methodological model developed on the basis of this approach made it possible to distinguish the following important stages in the process of communication with children:

the first stage - creating an atmosphere of trust;

the second - identifying the emotional needs of the child;

the third - forming methods of active listening to the child and responding to him;

the fourth - maintaining constant and consistent communication;

the fifth - ensuring emotional stability by continuing communication in conflict situations.

Specific psychological and communicative techniques were used for each stage. In particular, such methods as "positive reflection", "open questions", "building an emotional bridge", "paraphrasing" served to openly express the child's opinion and form a sense of self-esteem. Also, during the communication process, short psychological training sessions were organized for parents, where emotional literacy, patience and empathy in communication, non-punitive forms of encouraging the child, and strategies for behaving in stressful situations were taught through practical examples. The approaches put forward in these sessions were tested in real-life situations and showed their positive effect. In this case, the exchange of views, sharing of experiences and assessment of positive changes in children once again confirmed the viability and usefulness of the methodology. Based on the approach model created on the basis of the research methodology, it can be concluded that establishing communication with adopted children correctly is a complex psychological process that involves not only communication tools, but also emotional stability, trust, affection

and a conscious approach. Therefore, any practical activity in this area should be multi-stage, systematic and methodologically sound.

Analysis and results:

Analysis was conducted based on interviews with 20 selected families, psychological observation, and project tests to study the process of communication with adopted children. Particular attention was paid to the composition of the families, the age of the children, their gender, the length of time since adoption, and the forms of communication. The children participating in the study were between 6 and 15 years old, 55 percent of whom were boys and 45 percent were girls. 65 percent of the adopted children had been adopted into the family within the last three years, which indicates that the adaptation process is still ongoing. The criteria for assessing the quality of communication were: the level of trusting communication, emotional openness, the child's ability to express himself, the emotional response of the parents, and the consistency of communication. According to the results of the observation, it was found that in families with established trusting and stable communication, children had higher emotional stability, and the level of self-awareness and expression was relatively strong. Such families accounted for 40 percent of the total participants. On the contrary, in 35 percent of cases, ambiguity, coldness, or a one-sided approach to communication was observed. In these families, children were noted to have low self-esteem, communicative withdrawal, trust problems, and marked emotional instability. According to the results of the survey, 70 percent of parents admitted that they did not have sufficient information about the child's previous psychological trauma. Also, 60 percent of parents noted that they did not know what psychological techniques to use in communication. This indicates the need to increase the psychological literacy and communication competence of parents. In turn, after the introduction of communication techniques recommended to families based on psychological counseling (active listening, reflection, empathetic response), during a 4-week observation period, it was noted that 60 percent of children had increased positive emotional responses, gained confidence in their behavior, and increased openness to communication. Psychodiagnostic analyses conducted on the basis of the "I Draw My Family" project test showed that 75% of children who drew themselves as part of a family openly express their opinions and demonstrate more positive behavior in everyday communication. On the contrary, 80% of children who drew themselves on the sidelines, for example, in a corner or far from other members, felt isolated, unheard, or unappreciated in communication. This is directly related to the lack of emotional closeness. During the interview, it was found that the majority of parents conduct communication in the form of "advice", "education," that is, rather than an equal conversation with the child, conversations in a tone of instruction or reproach prevail. Such an approach leads to one-sided communication, and the child gradually begins to

accumulate internal resentment, indifference, or resentment. On the contrary, healthy communication can be seen to develop in families where the child's feelings are taken into account and he is seen as an active interlocutor.

Based on the above results, it can be said that the quality of communication in adoptive families directly affects the social and emotional development of the child. Especially against the background of traumatic experiences in childhood, the need for communication is strong, and if this need is not satisfied through conscious, loving, consistent communication, a state of constant instability arises in the child's psyche. Therefore, healthy communication is not only a means of conveying information through language, but also a means of strengthening the sense of social security through hearing, understanding the child's inner world and treating him with love. These scientific and practical analyses show that by systematically studying the communication process and introducing a conscious approach to it, it is possible to ensure the personal growth, family adaptation and emotional well-being of adopted children. This once again confirms the need to consider communication not only as an important factor of psychological, but also social stability.

Based on the above results, it is determined that the quality of communication has a significant impact not only on the child's emotional stability, but also on his social activity, self-confidence, and the level of mastering social roles. Warmth and consistency in communication are manifested as a positive factor in the child's behavior culture at school, relationships with peers, and general social adaptation. On the contrary, in families with cold, formal, and one-sided communication, the child distrusts the external environment, and passivity, social shyness, and in some cases, aggressiveness may appear in communication. This was also confirmed during observation and interviews.

Based on statistical generalizations, in 68 percent of children, the quality and stability of communication led to the formation of a positive self-esteem. Factors such as the time parents spend talking to the child separately every day, paying attention to their opinions, and emotional support played a key role in this. On the contrary, in families where parents have a purely controlling approach and communication styles that deny the child's emotional state, the child's self-esteem has decreased, and psychological defense mechanisms (silence, lying, isolation) have increased. Another important aspect is that the quality of family communication is also directly dependent on the relationship between parents. Parental relationships built on mutual respect, patience, and affection serve as a model for communication for the child. Therefore, in some families, it has been observed that the real cause of the child's emotional instability is the parents' cold or conflicting relationship with each other. In such cases, the child may experience internal conflict, feelings of guilt, anxiety, sleep disturbances, and changes in eating habits.

At the practical stage, a daily "parent-child conversation time" based on emotional communication was introduced in 6 families as a test. Every day, for at least 15-20 minutes, the child's feelings, experiences, and desires were listened to. After 3 weeks, the results of the observation showed that these sessions led to significant positive changes in the child's mood, level of confidence, and behavior. In particular, children's openness, affection for their parents, and free expression of their opinions increased by 70 percent. These statistical and qualitative analyses show that effective communication with adopted children is not only a matter of using psychological techniques, but also a process of reconsidering the entire family environment, forming a conscious, responsible, and consistent approach to communication. Success in communication ensures not only the child's spiritual recovery, but also his social integration and the restoration of a sense of control over his life. An important conclusion from the results is that communication with a child in adoptive families is not only a means of upbringing, but also a key resource that provides personal intimacy, emotional security, mental stability and personal freedom. Therefore, any scientific and practical work in this area should be based on deep psychological preparation, analysis of the social context and person-centered approaches.

Diagram 1. Analysis of the quality of communication with adopted children.

The diagram is based on an analysis of the quality of communication with adopted children, which reflects four main indicators. The green segment represents families with effective communication, which accounts for 40% of the total. The red segment represents families with coldness, disconnection, or ambiguity in communication, which accounts for 35%. The yellow segment indicates that parents are unaware of psychological techniques, which is typical for 60% of participants. The blue segment covers families where a communication-based approach has resulted in significant positive changes in the child, which is estimated at more than 70%. The diagram shows that the psychological readiness and emotional approach of parents are crucial in establishing effective communication with children.

Conclusions and recommendations.

International Journal of Pedagogics

Establishing effective communication with adopted children directly affects their mental state, social adaptation, and personal development. Timely and properly established communication restores the child's inner confidence, forms a sense of self-esteem and helps him find his place in the family environment. Parents with psychological knowledge and communication skills are successful in this process. On the contrary, in families with a cold or one-sided approach, children experience increased emotional instability, isolation, and dissatisfaction. This shows that communication is an important and decisive part of the child's adoption process.

- The formation of warm and trusting communication between the family and the child is the main guarantee of the child's mental health.
- The quality of communication significantly affects the child's social adaptation and behavioral behavior.
- The psychological literacy of adoptive parents is directly related to the child's emotional stability.
- The need for communication in children adopted after a traumatic experience is strong and continuous.
- Psychological training for parents will have a practical effect on improving communication.

Recommendations:

- Organize training and seminars for adoptive families aimed at developing special communication skills.
- Develop and distribute methodological guides that develop emotional communication with children.
- Establish permanent counseling services for adoptive families with the participation of local psychologists.
- Early identification and resolution of communication problems in children through timely psychological examinations.
- Promote a culture of communication in the adoption process through the media and educational institutions.

In order to form stable and healthy communication with adopted children, it is necessary to work systematically with families, which will include special training, psychological counseling, practical methodological guidelines and the formation of social support mechanisms, which will serve as a key factor in the child's full adaptation to the family, self-realization and the direction of his life in a positive direction.

REFERENCES:

1. G'oziyev E.G. Mamatov M.M. va boshqalar "O'spirin psixologiyasi" ToshD.U. 1992.

2. G'oziyev E.G Utanov B "Xamkorlik psixologiyasi" T., Tosh D.U. 1992
3. Lyaudis V.L. - Metodika prepodavaniya psixologii, iz.vo 2000.
4. Sulaymon Amirqulovich Xaydarov. (2024). O'quvchilarni tarbiyashda ijtimoiy fanlarni o'qitishni didaktik imkoniyatlari. SCIENCE AND EDUCATION SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL. 5.1.B.271-275
5. Khaydarov S, A. (2023). Using technologies in teaching social sciences. GALAXY INTERNATIONAL INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH JOURNAL (GIIRJ), (pp. 305-309). 11(9).
6. Хайдаров, С. (2023). Pedagogik faoliyatda o'qituvchi o'zida kompetentlik sifatlarini shakillantirishi. Цифровизация современного образования: проблема и решение, 1(1), 64–67. <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/digitalization-moderneducation/article/view/24652>
7. Khaydarov, S. A. The role of the use of fine arts in teaching the history of the country. International scientific and practical conference. CUTTING EDGESCIENCE. In Conference Proceedings (pp. 41-43).2021